

IMPLEMENTATION OF ETLE (ELECTRONIC TRAFFIC LAW ENFORCEMENT) POLICY AT POLDA METRO JAYA'S DITLANTAS

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Abstract

With the advancement of technology and information as a result of globalization, the government, especially the police, has taken advantage of technological advances to enable more effective and efficient electronic services. The implementation of the electronic ticketing program or commonly called ETLE is one of the services by utilizing technology and communication. In practice, it is hoped that the ticket management process will be easier to carry out. In general, a ticket is an abbreviation of "evidence of violation" in the field of road traffic and transportation as mandated in Law Number 22 of 2009 concerning Road Traffic and Transportation. At first, the ticketing mechanism was carried out conventionally by giving a ticket to the violator to then conduct a trial and pay a fine. This study uses a qualitative approach where researchers will interact with them, and try to understand their language and interpretation of the implementation of policies that are the focus of this research, while the results of this study explain that, the implementation of the electronic ticketing program (ETLE) carried out by the Ditlantas Polda Metro Jaya seen from the public dimension regarding communication and coordination between implementing agencies has been said to be good. With the e-ticketing policy (ETLE) that has been implemented, it is quite effective in suppressing the actions of extortionists and brokers, both from the internal police and other stakeholders/actors (prosecutors and courts) involved in the implementation/implementation of the e-ticket system. In addition to increasing the effectiveness of the process, it also creates transparency and accountability of Law Enforcement Officials (APH) in terms of payment of e-ticket fines.

Keywords: Implementation, Policy, Electronic traffic law enforcement

A.INTRODUCTION

The growth of science and technology that is intertwined certainly encourages significant changes in every activity of human life, one of which is the development of transportation facilities in the form of motorized vehicles used in everyday life. In the past, public transportation facilities were still traditional, for example horses with improvised equipment

as land transportation facilities, but along with advances in science and technology, the use of motorized vehicle transportation facilities has become so intensively taking over traditional transportation facilities. Like two sides of a coin, this condition not only has a positive impact but also has a negative impact. In addition to causing traffic jams as is often highlighted in the news in various mass media, both print and electronic media, the use of motorized vehicles that continues to increase so rapidly is also accompanied by an increase in the number of traffic violations that occur on highways. This very significant increase in the number of motorized vehicles is in fact not directly proportional to the accumulation of highway sections designated for motorized vehicles. These traffic violations are allegedly one of the aspects that influence the occurrence of various traffic accidents/accidents on the highway which have the potential to cause fatalities or material losses for motorists and/or other people who participate in the traffic accident.

In relation to technological developments, it can be said that the digital era is the embryo of the birth of digital technology-based public service reform in the government line, which is currently known as electronic government (e-government). Through e-government, all institutions are expected to be able to work quickly in providing excellent service to the public, including the Indonesian National Police (Polri) institution which is the function of state government in the field of security maintenance; public order; law enforcement; as well as protection, protection, and service to the community. Several forms of changes in public service activities carried out by the Indonesian National Police in the implementation of e-government can be monitored from a service condition that was previously slow to fast and from a process that was previously difficult it has now become more practical and economical.

One example of the knitted product of e-government inherent in the National Police, in particular the Directorate of Traffic (Ditlantas) Polda Metro Jaya, is the electronic ticketing program (e-ticket) or known as ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement), which has been in effect since November 2018. In general, ticketing is an abbreviation of “evidence of violation” in the field of road traffic and transportation as mandated in Law Number 22 of 2009 concerning Road Traffic and Transportation. At first, the ticketing mechanism was carried out conventionally by giving a ticket to the violator to then conduct a trial and pay a fine.

However, considering the increasing number of motorized vehicles and coupled with the proliferation of digital-based transportation systems in today's modern era, the potential for traffic violations is also increasing, so that the payment of fines by violators through the conventional system automatically also increases. In fact, this has actually ignited problems for the National Police as the front line of law enforcement officers, because conventional ticket payments open up many opportunities for abuse of authority from law enforcement officers, which is of course very contrary to the principle of public service and the real dignity of Polri's service. In order to overcome these problems, the National Police made a breakthrough in the e-ticketing policy (using a ticketing application) which consisted of a

manual ticketing program and an ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program. The manual ticketing program is a conventional ticketing program through field officers, which is then inputted into the e-ticket application system. Meanwhile, the ETLE program is a development of conventional ticketing by using electronic devices without a traffic ticket operation on the highway. Both programs are part of the e-ticket policy that is connected to the electronic payment system. The e-ticket program is a form of Polri's public service that is very beneficial to the community as well as an effort to eliminate the practice of brokering and extortion in Indonesia.

As previously explained, one of the implementations of the e-ticket policy is ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement), which is an implementation of technology to record traffic violations electronically in order to support traffic security, order and safety. The ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program is a traffic law enforcement system based on information technology using electronic devices in the form of cameras that can detect various types of traffic violations and present motorized vehicle data automatically (Automatic Number Plate Recognition), so that the whole ticketing process will be more efficient. The types of traffic violations that can be recorded by electronic equipment in the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program include odd-even violations, road signs and markings violations, speed limit violations, not using a safety belt, and using cell phones while driving.

Based on data from the Annual Report of the Gakkum Sub-Directorate of Traffic of the Polda Metro Jaya from 2017 to 2019, especially in the jurisdiction of the Polda Metro Jaya, the number of traffic violations during the 3 (three) year period experienced an increasing trend every year, where in 2017 the number of traffic violations traffic was 1,324,101 (one million three hundred twenty four thousand one hundred and one) violations, then increased in 2018 to 1,617,566 (one million six hundred seventeen thousand five hundred and sixty six) violations, and in 2019 again experienced an increase with the number of 1,698,271 (one million six hundred ninety eight thousand two hundred and seventy one) violations. Likewise, the number of traffic accidents is experiencing an increasing trend, where in 2018 there were 5,903 (five thousand nine hundred and three) traffic accidents, then increased in 2019 to 8,877 (eight thousand eight hundred seventy-seven) cases (Directorate of Traffic Polda Metro Jaya, 2020).

In particular, Law Number 22 of 2009 concerning Road Traffic and Transportation gives the Police the authority to take action against traffic violations and investigate traffic crimes, as regulated in Article 260 which contains the following:

- (1) In terms of taking action against violations and investigating criminal acts, Polri Investigators other than those stipulated in the Criminal Procedure Code and the Law on Polri, in the field of road traffic and transportation are authorized to:
 - a. To stop, prohibit, or delay the operation and temporarily confiscate motorized vehicles that are reasonably suspected of violating traffic regulations or are tools and/or proceeds of crime;

- b. To examine the truth of information relating to the investigation of criminal acts in the field of traffic and road transportation;
 - c. Request information from drivers, motorized vehicle owners, and/or public transportation companies;
 - d. c. confiscate the Driver's License, motorized vehicle, cargo, Motorized Vehicle Number Certificate, Motorized Vehicle Trial Certificate, and/or test pass as evidence;
 - e. Take action against criminal acts of traffic violations or crimes according to the provisions of laws and regulations;
 - f. Make and sign the minutes of inspection;
 - g. Stop the investigation if there is not enough evidence;
 - h. Make detentions related to traffic crimes; and/or take other actions according to law responsibly.
- (2) The prosecution of violations and the investigation of criminal acts as referred to in paragraph (1) shall be carried out in accordance with the provisions of the laws and regulations.

The realization of the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program is based on Article 272 of Law Number 22 of 2009 concerning Road Traffic and Transportation which states that to support enforcement activities for violations in the field of traffic and road transportation, electronic equipment can be used, while the results of the use This electronic equipment can be used as evidence in a court that was previously covered by law through the provisions of Article 5 paragraph (1) of Law Number 11 of 2008 concerning Electronic Information and Transactions. The provisions of Article 272 of Law Number 22 of 2009 concerning Road Traffic and Transportation are further regulated in Government Regulation Number 80 of 2012 concerning Procedures for Inspection of Motorized Vehicles on the Road and Enforcement of Traffic and Road Transportation Violations, which stipulates that the prosecution of violations traffic and road transportation is based on the results of: (a) Findings in the vehicle inspection process; (b) Reports; and/or (c) Records of electronic equipment.

With the e-ticket policy that has been implemented, in his research (Chusminah et al., 2018) argues, that this is quite effective in suppressing extortion and brokers, both from internal Polri and other stakeholders / actors (prosecutors and courts) involved in the implementation/implementation of the e-ticket system. In addition to increasing the effectiveness of the process, it also creates transparency and accountability of Law Enforcement Officials (APH) in terms of payment of e-ticket fines. The practice of implementing the e-ticket system has basically been carried out in all Polda, namely 33 (thirty three) Polda ranks during 2017, but in practice the application of e-ticketing can be said to be still not as expected or in other words not optimal.

Furthermore, in the study (Suhendriyo et al., 2019) it was stated that the implementation of e-tickets at the Tabalong Police Station, Tabalong Regency, South Kalimantan, had been

implemented well with a percentage of 59.2% (fifty-nine point two percent). This means that some people know about the process of paying ticket fines with the e-ticket mechanism at the Tabalong Resort Police which can provide benefits to the community. However, there are obstacles with the high percentage of the possibility of levies outside the procedure with a percentage of 80.0% (eighty point zero percent) and satisfaction with officers in providing e-ticketing services with a percentage of 16.7% (sixteen percent). point seven percent).

Based on the previous research, in order to continue to improve the quality of public e-ticket services through the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program after being implemented for approximately 2 (two) years, a study was conducted to understand the working mechanism and analyze the performance inhibiting factors in the implementation of the ETLE policy. (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) at Ditlantas Polda Metro Jaya. In addition, research on the implementation of this policy can contribute new findings in public policy science that can provide information about whether the policy is effective or not in implementing the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) policy at the Ditlantas Polda Metro Jaya.

Public Policy Concept

Public policy generally used to designate the behavior of a person (actor) or a group of people or an institution such as an official, group, or a government agency in a particular field of activity. In such a context, the meaning of policy can be used and is sufficient for ordinary conversations, but not sufficient for scientific discussions. Therefore, a more adequate concept or definition of public policy is needed. Experts provide various definitions of public policy according to their different backgrounds of expertise.

According to Thomas R. Dye (2005), public policy is "what government says and do, or not to do. It is the goals or purpose of government programs." Public policy is everything that is done or not done by the government, as well as the reasons a policy must be carried out and the benefits for common life must be a holistic consideration, so that the policy contains great benefits for the community and does not cause harm. This is where the government must be wise in setting a policy. Then, Anderson (1979) defines policy as a series of goals and objectives of government programs. Policy is a direction of action that has an intention set by an actor or a number of actors in overcoming a problem or a problem. Furthermore, according to Widodo (2011) policy is an effort to understand and interpret several things, including: (a) What is done (or not done) by the government regarding a problem; (b) What causes or affects it; and (c) What is the impact and impact of the public policy. Public policy is also seen as an attempt to achieve certain goals with certain means and in a certain time sequence. Furthermore, public policy is also interpreted as a process that causes a relationship between the government and its people as stated by Fadillah Putra (2003), that public policy is a concrete form of the process of contact between the state and its people.

From some of the opinions mentioned above, it can be concluded that public policy is a series of choices to do or not do something that results in contact between the government and its

people which contains elements such as broad goals and specific targets, as well as ways to achieve these goals. Formulated by a government agency or office.

Basically, every policy carried out by the government does not always have the same goal, but if you look closely, there are several characteristics that can be seen in every government policy. Wahab (2004) argues that a public policy has certain characteristics that other types of policies do not have. Some of the characteristics of policy are also stated by Anderson (1979) as mentioned below:

- a. Public policy is purposive, goal oriented behavior rather than random or change behavior. Every policy must have a purpose, meaning that in making a policy it should not just be made or because there is an opportunity to make it.
- b. Public policy consists of courses of action, rather than separate, discrete decisions or actions performed by government officials. That is, a policy does not stand alone and is separate from other policies, but is related to various policies in society and is oriented towards the implementation, interpretation and enforcement of the law.
- c. Policy is what government do not what they say will do or what they intend to do. Policy is what the government does, not what the government wants or intends to do.
- d. Public policy may be either negative or positive. Policies can be negative or prohibitive and can also be directives to implement or encourage.
- e. Public policy is based on law and is authoritative. Policies are based on law, because they have the power to force people to obey them.

As a complex process, the policy process must involve various activities and variables to be studied. Experts divide the process into stages in order to facilitate the study of public policy. Shafritz and Russel (1997) formulated the following policy stages: (a) Setting the agenda; (b) The decision to do or not to do the policy; (c) Implementation; (d) Evaluation and analysis of program impacts; and (e) feedback. Furthermore, Dunn (1999) suggests that the policy stages include: (a) Setting the agenda; (b) Policy formulation; (c) Adoption of policies; (d) Policy implementation; and (e) Policy evaluation. Meanwhile, Carl V. Patton and David S. Savicky (in Nugroho, 2008) formulated the policy stages consisting of: (a) Defining the problem; (b) Determine the evaluation criteria; (c) Identify alternative policies; (d) Evaluating alternative policies; (e) Selecting preferred policies; and (f) Implement preferred policies.

Thus, it can be understood that basically the study of public policy is oriented towards solving real problems that occur in the community. Therefore, public policy analysis is generally an applied science and acts as a tool or science that seeks to solve problems.

Public Policy Implementation

To be able to measure whether a policy is successful or not, of course, it is seen from whether the policy objectives are achieved or not. Vice versa, it is said to be unsuccessful if the policy objectives are not achieved. The failure of a policy is often caused by the policy cannot be implemented, considering that the most important stage after a public policy is established is how the decision is implemented. In principle, policy implementation is a way for a policy

to achieve its goals. Based on the opinion of Dunn (2008), the implementation of a public policy is a process that is inherent in the public policy itself. That is, the implementation of public policy is a process that is (supposedly) designed in conjunction with the design of the relevant public policy. In line with that, Merilee S. Grindle (1980) said that implementation has the task of "to establish a link that allows the goals of public policies to be realized as outcomes of governmental activity." Implementation is a bridge that connects the goals of public policy with the desired reality. Implementation according to Pressman and Wildavsky (1973) is "to carry out, accomplish, fulfill, produce, complete." From this understanding, implementation can be expressed as an activity to perfect what is desired by policy makers, which also means to produce something desired by policy makers. From the various expert opinions, it can be concluded that implementation can be interpreted as an activity to implement a policy as outlined in a regulation issued by the government or other state institutions in order to achieve the objectives outlined in the policy. If the implementation process has been running, it is expected that an output will appear, namely immediate results (effect) and final impact (impact). Immediate results are the short-term effects or consequences produced by a policy implementation, while policy impacts are a number of consequences generated by policy implementation through a long-term process. Immediate results and impacts will be very useful for assessing the implementation of a policy.

Policy Process

Policy is "whatever governments choose to do or not to do," which means all forms of actions or decisions that the government chooses to do or not to do (Thomas R. Dye: 2005). Parson (2006) describes the policy process as a cycle and is called the policy life cycle. The policy process is a dynamic cycle and continues to go hand in hand with the development of conditions and the surrounding environment. Starting from the existence of a problem (problem), then alternative steps are chosen to be taken, then the choice is implemented and then the policy will be evaluated. From the evaluation results, information will be obtained to what extent the program or policy has implications for the community.

Source: *Dunn, 1999.*

Another interesting model that also belongs to the category of synthesis model and attracts the attention of many experts is the 'integrated implementation model' developed by Winter (2004), where they view implementation as something that does not stand alone. Soren

introduces his view as an 'integrated model.' The integrated model (integrated model) shows that the success of implementation is determined from the formulation, implementation process, to policy outcomes, which themselves have a link between political and administrative processes, as shown in the following figure:

Source: Winter, 2004.

Based on the picture, it is clear that policy implementation is strongly influenced by policy design which is basically born or determined from the policy formulation itself. Another thing that also influences is the socio-economic condition of the community. A policy may be greatly affected by the recipient of the policy in which the policy is implemented. According to Winter, the implementation itself is related to the behavior of related organizations, the behavior of the lower level bureaucracy as policy implementers, and is related to the behavior of the policy target groups.

The variables that affect the policy implementation process are as follows:

a. Organizational and Inter-Organizational Behavior

The dimensions are commitment and coordination between organizations. The implementation of public policies in achieving optimal results rarely takes place with their own group without using other organizations as supporters or implementing tools. Policy implementation requires inter-organizational relationships to bring general policy changes into clear rules, and takes place in a sustainable manner in a social process that can shift land use policy directions through action.

b. Street Level Bureaucratic Behavior

The dimension is discretion. The next variable that becomes a key factor in policy implementation is the behavior of the lower-level bureaucracy. This is intended as the ability and willingness to implement and carry out programs as important decisions by using a more dominant influence outside the formal authority (discretion). According to Lipsky (1980) in (Parawangi, 2011), the behavior of implementing policies

systematically sometimes 'deviates' from tasks related to the authority as policy implementers.

c. Target Group Behavior

The behavior of the target group (target group behavior) not only influences the effects/impacts of policies, but also affects the performance of lower-level bureaucrats/apparatuses. Its dimensions include the positive and negative responses of the community in supporting or not supporting the policy. The behavioral variable of the target group in the implementation of public policy is a group of people, organizations, or individual policy recipients who play a role not only in terms of policy impact, but also in influencing program implementation performance through positive and negative actions (Winter, 2004). Thus, the performance of program implementation is strongly influenced by the characteristics of participation, namely supporting or rejecting. This model is a framework that presents the mechanism and becomes a key factor that can affect the final outcome of an implementation. About who is the target group whose behavior will be influenced by the policy and how far it can comply or adapt to the implemented policy, it really depends on the suitability of the content of the policy (program) with their expectations.

Based on the explanation above, the analysis carried out to find out about the ETLT policy will be reviewed through three criteria or variables in the implementation of the policy.

A. METHOD

In this study, a qualitative approach was used to identify and describe the ETLT (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) policy in terms of 3 (three) criteria in implementing the policy. While the reason for using quantitative research methods is to find out the response from the community regarding the implementation of the ETLT (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) policy. The reason for using qualitative methods in this research is because in essence this research observes and describes the process of implementing policies that involve people in their environment. Therefore, researchers will interact with them, and try to understand their language and interpretation of the implementation of policies that are the focus of this research. Through the use of qualitative methods, it is hoped that the data obtained will be more complete, more in-depth, as well as more credible and meaningful, so that the research objectives can be achieved. Furthermore, the description will be used to find the principles and explanations that lead to conclusions.

B. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Organizational and Inter-Organizational Behavior

a. Inter-Organizational Commitment

Based on the findings in the field, it is known that inter-organizational commitment can be described through the relationship or cooperation carried out by the Ditlantas Polda Metro Jaya and the Ministry of Empowerment of State Apparatus-Bureaucratic Reform (Kemenpan-RB), Courts, Provincial Government/Pemda DKI Jakarta, Population Service and Civil Registry (Disdukcapil) Jakarta, Pos Indonesia, Bank

Rakyat Indonesia (BRI), as well as internet service providers and telecommunications network providers in terms of cooperation agreements. The collaboration was marked by the existence of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) related to the implementation of the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program in the DKI Jakarta area. This is proof that there has been a commitment between organizations/institutions or stakeholders to carry out the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program in accordance with the mandate of the legislation.

The most prominent commitment was shown by the pioneers or the initiators of ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) which emerged during the Kombospol Polda Metro Jaya era from 2004 to 2008, which was then followed up with a trial of prosecution. However, the trial at that time did not use an ANPR (Automatic Number Plate Recognition)-based camera as is used now, but only used an ordinary monitoring camera, where traffic violations were photographed by officers through cameras manually, which was then used as evidence of violations at the time of the incident. send a warning letter to the owner of a motorized vehicle that commits a violation.

Furthermore, in the era of Kombespol Polda Metro Jaya in 2012-2013, the camera changed its function to be socializing to the public in the form of traffic violations and socialization in traffic prevention, but has not yet entered the realm of law violations, considering its nature is only socialization or control. Then in 2018, ETLE was again activated and made effective after the implementation of the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) with experts, legal practitioners, and related stakeholders. Departing from the results of the FGD, the idea of ETLE emerged as it is currently being implemented, namely by placing surveillance cameras at traffic lights in the Sarinah area and the Indosat Roundabout. Both cameras function as e-police cameras to photograph traffic violations, such as violators crossing red lights or apill and road markings. At that time the camera used could only take pictures of the two types of violations.

There is a fairly long period of time passed by the Ditlantas Polda Metro Jaya to be able to finalize the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program since the idea was first conceived. However, apart from this, there is a real commitment from the Ditlantas Polda Metro Jaya who always communicates with position holders such as the Kemenpan-RB, Disdukcapil, and other stakeholders in order to carry out the socialization process gradually to the community.

b. Inter-Organizational Coordination

Based on the findings in the field, it is known that there has been communication or coordination between stakeholders involved in the implementation of the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program. This is evident from the absence of significant obstacles in the process of signing the MoU, disbursement of fines, division of duties for ticket executors (back office officers, prosecutors' officers, bank officers, and the provincial/local government). This good cooperation and

coordination can be seen from the success of collecting fines throughout 2020 of approximately Rp. 12 (twelve) billion rupiah which is declared as state income from the results of the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program. On the other hand, coordination between these organizations is a form of commitment in realizing the mandate of the legislation for the common good.

Over time, ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) was recognized as a creative breakthrough and became the flagship policy of the National Police Chief, as well as a form of Polda Metro Jaya's efforts to approach the DKI Jakarta Provincial Government who were invited to the meeting forum. The presentation at the forum was the superiority of the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) policy, because if you look back, this program is the first breakthrough made by the National Police, especially the Jakarta area which acts as a pilot project.

2. Street Level Bureaucratic Behavior

Based on the findings in the field, it is known that the implementation of the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) policy at the Ditlantas Polda Metro Jaya has been running properly in accordance with the ability and willingness to implement and run the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program as an important decision by using the influence more dominant than the Central Police.

In the practice of implementing the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program in the Polda Metro Jaya area, there were several obstacles encountered, such as the presence of some people who did not agree and chose other paths such as taking legal action to court, because they did not accept being subject to an electronic ticket. However, on the other hand, the evidence from photos and videos produced by ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) cameras is very helpful in defending decisions on violations committed during the court process. This is certainly a challenge for the Ditlantas Polda Metro Jaya to be more aggressive in carrying out the socialization process about ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) for bureaucrats at lower levels and also especially for ordinary people who do not know about the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) policy in the area. Polda Metro Jaya law. Leaving aside these twists and turns, it is undeniable that the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program has had a positive impact on the DKI Jakarta Provincial Government in overcoming congestion, because the policy synergizes as a control to supervise/ticket motor vehicles during odd and even application periods.

Throughout the implementation of the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program so far, it can be said that there is a trend of changing the behavior of community groups or vehicle users, although this requires a fairly long process. The process began with the implementation of ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) in November 2018 which was followed by a trial for 1 (one) month where in December 2018 the Ditlantas Polda Metro Jaya took the first action and found many violations that occurred.

In its implementation, apart from technical problems, there were also obstacles related to the operational budget. For example, the cost for sending a confirmation letter by postal giro is

IDR 6,300 (six thousand three hundred rupiah) per letter. Assuming that you have to send 500 (five hundred) confirmation letters, it means that you need funds of around Rp. 3,150,000 (three million one hundred and fifty thousand rupiahs), while the amount of budget received by the police is still limited, so that the process of prosecution tends to be adjusted to the amount of the budget required. There all along.

3. Target Group Behavior

Based on the findings in the field, it is known that there are various reactions from every community involved in ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) ticketing. The action carried out by the Polda Metro Jaya through procedures including collecting evidence of violations and sending a confirmation letter of fines to the address of the violator according to the address of the police number (nopol) of the motorized vehicle. However, there are pros and cons in the procedure, as evidenced by the many lawsuits against the courts that were filed by traffic violators to the police officers on duty. There are also counters posted by several anti-corruption activists who think that the funding for the ETLE policy is too high and in vain, because they have to spend a lot of money for a surveillance camera that costs Rp. 230 (two hundred and thirty) million rupiahs to Rp.250. (two hundred and fifty million) rupiah for 1 (one) camera unit. Nevertheless, the pro side was obtained from academics and practitioners who fully support the policy in accordance with the results of the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) which was held together with the stakeholders involved in it.

The negative response from the public and certain circles allegedly emerged due to the lack of socialization carried out by the Polda Metro Jaya to the general public in their jurisdiction. It is undeniable, there is still a need for more targeted socialization by involving television service providers, influencers, and also legal observers to jointly implement the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) policy and follow every policy point stated in accordance with the mandate of the legislation. . Thus, the positive response received at this time is expected to be able to build public trust to comply with all forms of existing laws, not just the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) policy.

Over time, in the implementation of ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement), it was found that at this time there had been a change in the culture of the community to become more orderly in driving. This is concluded from data that shows a decreasing trend in the number of traffic violations along protocol roads in the DKI Jakarta area. For example, the number of traffic violations on the Thamrin road decreased by 44% (forty four percent), which was followed by the number of accidents which also decreased, due to the presence of ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) cameras in the area. Previously, drivers tended to stop in front of the stop line at a red light, now drivers are more orderly to stop behind the stop line, because they realize that there is an ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) camera that can capture traffic violations they commit. . The data also shows that points equipped with ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) cameras are increasingly showing a decreasing trend in the number of traffic violations.

D. CONCLUSION

The implementation of the electronic ticketing program carried out by the Ditlantas Polda Metro Jaya is seen from the dimensions of the ideal policy regarding communication and coordination between implementing agencies already said well. Meanwhile, communication between the implementing agency and the community has not been maximized interaction in socializing e-ticket program by the implementing agency to the community not completely covers the whole community so that it is not known and understood by community about existing programs and clarity of e-ticketing procedures. The realization of the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program is based on Article 272 of Law Number 22 of 2009 concerning Road Traffic and Transportation which states that to support enforcement activities for violations in the field of traffic and road transportation, electronic equipment can be used, while the results of the use This electronic equipment can be used as evidence in a court that was previously covered by law through the provisions of Article 5 paragraph (1) of Law Number 11 of 2008 concerning Electronic Information and Transactions. In addition, the implementation of e-tickets has reached a percentage of 59. This means that some people are aware of the process of paying ticket fines using the e-ticket mechanism. However, there are obstacles with the high percentage of the possibility of levies outside the procedure with a percentage of 80.0% and satisfaction with officers in providing e-ticketing services with a percentage of 16.7%, in order to continue to improve the quality of e-ticketing public services. Through the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) program after being implemented for approximately 2 years, a study was conducted to understand the working mechanism and analyze the performance inhibiting factors in implementing the ETLE (Electronic Traffic Law Enforcement) policy at the Ditlantas Polda Metro Jaya.

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